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**Artificial Intelligence and Deep Learning in Wedding Photo and Video Content
Creation**

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***Abstract.** The study's relevance is due to the growing need for fast, high-quality, personalized production of wedding photo and video content that combines artistic expression and technological efficiency. In this context, using artificial intelligence algorithms to transform creative processes deserves special attention. The article aims to study the potential of using artificial intelligence and deep learning in creating wedding visual content with a focus on improving the efficiency, quality, and level of individualization of the result.*

The paper applies methods of comparative analysis of the functional characteristics of modern AI-based tools, structural and semantic generalization of their application areas, and elements of practical modeling of the processes of stylistic adaptation and emotional processing of images and videos. The authors investigate the conceptual foundations of the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies into visual art and describe the use of their capabilities in the wedding segment, in

particular in the areas of stylization, editing, semantic structuring and quality optimization.

The study found that deep learning contributes to the artistic coherence of a visual product by maintaining compositional logic, preserving the emotional context, and reproducing the author's style. The study identified key problems that complicate the integration of solutions based on artificial intelligence technologies: technical limitations of infrastructure, standardization of visual solutions, and ethical risks regarding the reliability and confidentiality of images. The expediency of using artificial intelligence tools as an auxiliary tool for optimizing the creative process while maintaining control over the artistic result is proven.

The practical value of the study lies in the substantiation of mechanisms for the effective implementation of artificial intelligence systems in the professional activities of videographers and photographers.

Prospects for further research are related to the creation of specialized visual datasets, hybrid quality control models and adaptive learning platforms for training specialists in the field of wedding media production.

Keywords: *visual art, automated editing, image stylization, aesthetic processing, emotional expressiveness.*

Штучний інтелект і глибинне навчання у створенні весільного фото- та відеоконтенту

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***Анотація.** Актуальність дослідження зумовлена зростанням потреби у швидкому, якісному та персоналізованому виробництві весільного фото- та відеоконтенту, що поєднує художню виразність і технологічну ефективність. У цьому контексті на особливу увагу заслуговує використання алгоритмів штучного інтелекту як інструменту трансформації творчих процесів. Метою статті є дослідження потенціалу використання штучного інтелекту та глибинного навчання у створенні весільного візуального контенту з акцентом на підвищення ефективності, якості та рівня індивідуалізації результату.*

У роботі застосовано методи порівняльного аналізу функціональних характеристик сучасних інструментів на базі штучного інтелекту, структурно-змістове узагальнення напрямів їх застосування, а також елементи практичного моделювання процесів стилістичної адаптації та емоційної обробки зображень і відео. Авторами досліджено концептуальні засади впровадження технологій штучного інтелекту до візуального мистецтва, описано використання їхніх можливостей у весільному сегменті, зокрема у напрямках стилізації, монтажу, семантичного структурування та оптимізації якості.

У результаті дослідження встановлено, що глибинне навчання сприяє художній узгодженості візуального продукту через підтримку композиційної логіки, збереження емоційного контексту та відтворення авторської стилістики. У ході роботи виявлено ключові проблеми, які ускладнюють інтеграцію рішень на основі технологій штучного інтелекту: технічні обмеження інфраструктури, стандартизація візуальних рішень, етичні ризики щодо достовірності та конфіденційності зображень. Доведено доцільність застосування інструментів штучного інтелекту як допоміжного засобу для оптимізації творчого процесу за умови збереження контролю за художнім результатом.

Практична цінність дослідження полягає в обґрунтуванні механізмів ефективного впровадження систем штучного інтелекту до професійної діяльності відеографів і фотографів.

Перспективи подальших досліджень пов'язані зі створенням спеціалізованих візуальних датасетів, гібридних моделей контролю якості та адаптивних навчальних платформ для підготовки фахівців у сфері весільного медіавиробництва.

***Ключові слова:** візуальне мистецтво, автоматизований монтаж, стилізація зображень, естетична обробка, емоційна виразність.*

Problem statement. In today's context of rapid development of digital technologies and growing demand for personalized visual content, there is a need to rethink traditional approaches to creating wedding photo and video products. Standardization of aesthetic solutions, limited technical resources, and significant time spent on material processing are becoming factors that hinder the innovative development of this area. In this regard, the use of artificial intelligence and deep learning as tools for automation, creative modeling, and improving the quality of the final product is becoming particularly relevant. The problem lies not only in improving the technical process but also in the need to create new algorithmic solutions that can adapt to the emotional and individual context of wedding events. This, in turn, necessitates a scientific understanding of the relationship between technological innovations and the aesthetic expectations of users, as well as the development of practical models for integrating artificial intelligence into the creative processes of photography and video editing.

Thus, solving this problem is important both for the scientific community exploring the potential of artificial intelligence technologies in media production and

for practitioners interested in optimizing the processes of creating unique wedding content with a high level of artistic value.

Analysis of the latest research and publications. The analysis of scientific research shows that the use of artificial intelligence and deep learning in the creation of wedding photo and video content is taking place in four main areas.

The first area covers the automation of technical processes for creating visual content, including image processing and video generation. T. Ohanian's work [1] highlights how artificial intelligence algorithms are transforming traditional content creation methodologies by changing editing, composition, and processing automation. Researcher T. Zhai [2] demonstrates the principles of generating short videos using deep learning models that mimic real stylistic patterns inherent in the wedding genre. A group of scientists, P. Logeswari, B. India, N. Jebaraj, and G. BanuPriya [3], conducted a comparative analysis of video production tools, emphasizing their effectiveness in fast editing with the use of artificial intelligence technologies. It is advisable to supplement research in this area with empirical comparisons of the performance of manual and automated editing, taking into account the genre specifics of wedding videos. The second direction is related to the generation of text descriptions and scenarios using AI, which helps to improve the narration in wedding videos. The publication of S. Amirian, K. Rasheed, T. Taha, and H. Arabnia [4] summarizes approaches to the automatic creation of captions for images and videos with a focus on the romantic context and subjectivity of interpretations. A group of authors, S. Li, Z. Tao, K. Li, and Y. Fu [5], outline the concept of transition from image to text, which can be used in the scripting of wedding videos. Scientists J. Krohn, G. Beyleveld, and A. Bassens [6] illustrate the architectures of deep networks used for such transformations. However, it is worth supplementing these studies by creating training

datasets containing wedding terminology and emotionally colored texts adapted to the peculiarities of event description.

The third area covers the use of artificial intelligence technologies in the artistic and aesthetic transformation of visual material. The Chinese researcher Q. Yao [7] analyzes the use of virtual images in photography, in particular for creating aestheticized portraits and images of spouses in stylized settings. The authors G. Jeon, M. Anisetti, E. Damiani, and B. Kantarci [8] point out the possibility of identifying key visual patterns, such as smiles, gestures, or emotional moments, characteristic of wedding photography. A group of researchers, R. Saritha, V. Paul, and P. Kumar [9], demonstrate the effectiveness of image search by content in large archives of wedding photo shoots. The study recommends supplementing these works by analyzing the impact of intelligent filters on the aesthetic perception of users and studying the preferences of cultural specificity. The fourth area concerns the socio-cultural aspects of the use of artificial intelligence technologies in the field of wedding photo and video space. Researcher C. Hawley [10] criticizes the racial bias of algorithms that is manifested in popular Lightroom presets used in wedding photography, emphasizing the need for cultural sensitivity.

Authors M. Walsh and M. Wade [11] investigate how music selected by algorithms enhances romantic memory in video by affecting the emotional component. The group of authors T. Nguyen, Q. Nguyen, D. Nguyen, D. Nguyen, T. Huynh-Ze, S. Nahavandi, T. Nguyen, C. Pham, S. Nguyen [12] analyzes the risks of deepfake technologies, emphasizing the need for authenticity in documenting weddings. Researchers L. Liu, H. Hu, Y. Luo, and Y. Wen [13] substantiate the advantages of optimized real-time video streaming that can be used during broadcasts of wedding events. The author S. Erdem [14] demonstrates a new editing paradigm involving artificial intelligence technologies, where the algorithm acts as a co-author of the emotional structure of the video. For content creators, it is advisable to supplement

research in this area with ethical recommendations, considering privacy, social stereotypes, and copyright. The overall analysis shows that integrating artificial intelligence and deep learning technologies into wedding photo and video content opens up opportunities for automation, personalization, aesthetization, and critical thinking about technology.

Further research requires an interdisciplinary approach, considering aesthetic, technical, social, and ethical components.

Identification of previously unsolved parts of the overall problem. Despite the growing scientific interest in applying artificial intelligence in visual art, certain aspects of its use in wedding photography and video production remain insufficiently studied. First, we are talking about the theoretical justification of the artistic relevance of artificial intelligence models in genres with a high emotional load and the lack of a comprehensive analysis of the adaptation of deep learning to the needs of compositional logic and stylistic integrity of wedding content. The methodological limitations are manifested in the narrowness of the empirical base, which is focused mainly on general selection or classification algorithms without considering the specifics of individual events.

The proposed study aims to overcome these shortcomings by analyzing artificial intelligence tools' functionality in the wedding industry context, identifying ethical, technical and creative obstacles, and formulating practical solutions for the effective implementation of relevant technologies. This approach allows not only the expansion of the scientific understanding of the role of intelligent systems in artistic production but also the creation of an applied basis for the further development of tools focused on the needs of wedding media market professionals.

Formulating the goals of the article (task statement)

The article aims to study the possibilities of applying artificial intelligence and deep learning in creating wedding photo and video content to increase the efficiency, quality and individualization of visual material.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been identified:

1. To investigate the conceptual foundations and features of adaptation of artificial intelligence and deep learning to artistic expression requirements, stylistic integrity and emotional component in creating wedding photo and video content.

2. To analyze the functionality of modern artificial intelligence tools used to generate, process, and optimize images and videos in the wedding industry, considering their technical, aesthetic, and scenario parameters.

3. To identify the key problems of introducing intelligent technologies into the field of wedding media production and develop practical recommendations for effectively integrating AI-based solutions into the professional activities of photographers and videographers.

Presentation of the primary research material. Integrating artificial intelligence and deep learning into the visual arts is based on a conceptual combination of creative vision and algorithmic capabilities of computer data processing. In wedding photo and video content, these technologies allow not only to automate certain stages of production but also to bring the creative process to a new level - with elements of personalization, adaptation to the emotional context, and stylistic consistency. Deep learning, which operates with multi-level artificial neural networks, ensures the recognition of complex visual patterns, the modeling of aesthetic characteristics of an image, and the construction of a plot-logical video sequence based on behavioral and compositional signals. The main areas of implementation of such technologies in the context of visual art are shown in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1

Conceptual directions of artificial intelligence application in the creation of wedding photo and video content

Conceptual direction of artificial intelligence application	The essence of the application	Value in creating wedding content
Automated interpretation of visual information	Analysis of composition, facial expressions, scene dynamics	Facilitates the selection of the most emotionally rich and technically successful personnel
Semantic structuring of stories	Building an editing logic based on visual and behavioral features	Forms a complete story of the wedding day without the need for a traditional script
Modeling of artistic style	Simulate different stylistic approaches to photo and video processing	Provides personalized content based on aesthetic preferences
Frame-by-frame quality optimization	Enhance clarity, color and lighting correction	Improves the technical quality of visual material without manual intervention
Perception of emotions and dynamics	Identify moments with a high emotional load	Allows you to form an emotionally enriched narrative structure of the video

Source: systematized by the author on the basis of [2; 6; 10; 11; 12].

The areas shown in Table 1 demonstrate the interdisciplinary nature of introducing artificial intelligence into artistic visual production. Automated interpretation of visual information makes it possible to analyze dozens or hundreds of images to identify the most emotional and technically perfect shots without manual review. Semantic storytelling allows you to model a video narrative according to the logic of the event, for example, to identify the sequence "gathering-ceremony-

celebration" by the nature of images, movements, and scene type [4]. Artistic style modeling involves adjusting processing parameters according to predefined stylistic patterns, making it possible to create personalized content without deep manual post-processing. Image quality optimization is realized through automatic noise reduction, color correction, exposure balancing, etc., which is especially important in shooting conditions with difficult lighting or rapid scene changes.

The newest trend is algorithmic emotion detection - several systems analyze facial expressions, intonations, and scene dynamics to help create touching and emotionally charged video fragments [14]. These areas create an intellectual basis for rethinking the role of the photographer and videographer as a creative person who interacts with the algorithm in creating a visual product. The modern wedding industry is actively integrating AI-based tools that can not only automate routine processes but also improve the artistic quality of visual content by adapting it to the aesthetic expectations of the consumer. Developing deep learning, computer vision algorithms, and generative models has led to many software solutions covering the entire production cycle, from shooting to post-processing. These tools combine the functions of image processing, automatic editing, styling, retouching, color correction, quality improvement, removal of unnecessary objects, and generation of visual effects. The peculiarity of using such systems in the wedding segment is their ability to work with emotional material, preserving the liveliness and naturalness of the scene.

Table 2 shows the most common practical artificial intelligence tools wedding photo and video production specialists use.

Table 2

Functionality of modern AI tools for creating wedding photo and video content

Name of the tool	Type of artificial intelligence technology	Main functions in wedding production
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Luminar Neo (Skylum)	AI retouching, deep segmentation, masking	Automatic skin retouching, background removal, lighting enhancement, sky replacement
Topaz Video AI	Super resolution, noise reduction, frame rate scaling (FPS)	Improve video quality, stabilize, preserve details when scaling
Runway ML	Generative video, intelligent object removal	Create a video based on text prompts, remove people or objects from the scene
Adobe Photoshop (Adobe Sensei)	Object recognition, generative filling	AI retouching, composition changes, image generation by description
Magisto (Vimeo)	AI editing, emotional structuring	Automatically create a wedding video based on faces, scenes, and music rhythm
PortraitPro	Specialized AI portrait processing	Improving facial expressions, correcting facial features, styling according to templates

Source: author's own development

All of these tools are actively used in professional wedding photography practice, offering users flexible, functional solutions for each stage of working with visual material. The Luminar Neo tool [15] by Skylum features the latest automatic masking system based on artificial intelligence technologies, automatic face retouching, sky and lighting replacement according to the depth of the scene, which allows achieving a cinematic effect even in difficult shooting conditions. Topaz Video AI [16] specializes in video processing and is used to stabilize, increase frame rates, and improve the clarity and detail of recordings, functions that are especially in demand when processing video from drones or cameras without a stabilizer. Runway ML [17] provides the ability to work with generative models: the user can remove unnecessary objects, replace the background, or even create new videos based on text prompts, which opens up new possibilities for creative post-processing of wedding stories.

Adobe Photoshop, integrated with the Adobe Sensei platform [18], allows for intelligent object segmentation, image reconstruction, stylization, and generation of new elements in photos; this allows for quick correction of composition flaws without losing artistry. The Magisto tool [19], developed by Vimeo, is used to automatically edit short wedding videos: it analyzes emotions on faces, scene changes, and event dynamics and synchronizes footage with music to create a professional video in minutes. PortraitPro [20] is another highly specialized tool designed for automated portrait processing, including skin correction, facial relief, symmetry, and facial expressions, which is especially important in wedding photo shoots. Together, these solutions significantly reduce post-processing time, preserving the individuality of the image and expanding the creative possibilities of the videographer. Adapting deep learning algorithms to the needs of wedding photo and video production goes beyond traditional technical processing and involves a complex interaction between the computational model and the artistic and emotional nature of the visual material.

The main challenge in this context is to reconfigure standard neural networks focused on object classification or segmentation to tasks requiring subtle stylistic interpretation, conveying the scene's mood, and maintaining aesthetic integrity throughout the project. New generation deep networks allow you to work with the semantic characteristics of images, taking into account the style, rhythm, atmosphere, and even the narrative sequence of frames. Such adaptation is carried out through specialized training samples, customized feature loss, and generative models that can imitate artistic style or compositional patterns (Table 3).

Table 3

Features of adaptation of deep learning algorithms to the artistic requirements
of wedding photo and video content

The aspect of artistic adaptation	Features of the implementation of deep learning	Examples of influence on wedding content
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Stylistic integrity	Application of stylistic filters and style transfer through neural networks	Maintain the same color tone, textures and chiaroscuro in all frames of a wedding album or video
Emotional compliance	Training models on emotionally labeled data, focus on facial expressions and gestures	Highlighting the shots with the most expressive facial expressions or the dynamics of the couple's interaction
Compositional harmony	Optimization of framing based on the rules of the “golden ratio”, symmetry and background	Automatically create visually balanced scenes when editing video or creating slideshows
Preserving the rhythm and atmosphere	Recurrent models work with dynamic sequences	Ensuring smooth transitions between scenes, taking into account emotional tension and musical accompaniment
Stylization in artistic representation	Generate images or video clips based on artistic styles	Imitation of pastel finishes, vintage film or cinematic presentation according to customer wishes

Source: systematized by the author based on [2; 5; 8; 9; 10; 14].

In modern conditions, such adaptation is realized through pre-training models on visual material containing emotionally charged scenes and customized interfaces that allow manual adjustment of elements of artistic expression. For example, stylistic integrity is achieved through style transfer algorithms that consider the color palette and the texture, lighting type, and compositional characteristics inherent in wedding photography in a particular region or tradition.

Emotional relevance is ensured by pre-labeling image sets with the degree of emotional load, which allows the model to recognize key moments of interaction between people and focus on them.

Compositional harmony, in turn, is built in at the level of framing and staging of scenes, which allows for avoiding fragmentation and maintaining the logic of the visual narrative. Preserving the rhythm and atmosphere in the video is achieved through recurrent architectures that adapt to the internal dynamics of the event and the music.

Thanks to such solutions, deep learning has turned becomes a tool for artistic media modeling, capable of working not only with pixels but also with aesthetic categories previously considered the exclusive prerogative of the human mind.

The introduction of intelligent technologies in the wedding media production industry is accompanied by several key issues that significantly affect the quality of the result, the creative autonomy of the videographer, and the legal security of the customer.

One of the main obstacles is the limited versatility of deep learning algorithms, which are not always able to adequately respond to unpredictable shooting conditions, lighting changes, sudden dynamics, or individual peculiarities of emotional expression. Even with a high level of automation, artificial intelligence systems require constant human supervision, as misinterpreted scenes can destroy the narrative logic or deprive the video of emotional authenticity [8]. At the same time, there are difficulties in preserving the videographer's creative style, as using standard AI models leads to the unification of stylistic solutions, which reduces the uniqueness of the product and can level the author's handwriting. Technical problems also relate to hardware compatibility and performance: processing large amounts of video data requires powerful graphics processors, a significant amount of RAM, and a stable software environment, which is not always available to freelance professionals or small studios [4].

Ethical risks include the unauthorized generation or alteration of faces, context, or emotional presentation using artificial intelligence technologies, which can distort real events and cause distrust in the authenticity of the material [14]. The issue of

confidentiality requires special attention: some services operate in cloud environments that potentially do not guarantee the safety of private information about the couple and guests [6]. These problems emphasize the need not only for technology but also for regulatory regulation of the use of artificial intelligence technologies in wedding content, as well as for developing ethical standards that will ensure a balance between innovation, artistry, and responsibility. Effective integration of artificial intelligence technologies into the professional activities of photographers and videographers requires a systematic approach focused on a flexible combination of technological capabilities and creative tasks of the wedding services market.

First, it is advisable to introduce artificial intelligence tools as auxiliary tools for automating routine production stages: primary frame filtering, basic retouching, video stabilization, and color correction. This will free up resources for developing a creative concept, scenario structuring of the video sequence, and stylistic elaboration of the visual story.

One of the priority areas is the personalization of processing with the help of neural networks trained on the author's portfolio, which allows you to maintain an individual style while scaling processing. It is recommended to create your datasets for training models by the aesthetic preferences of the target audience, for example, considering traditions, regional color schemes, or typical wedding compositions of a certain format.

Using generative models to create splash screens, titles, stylized transitions, or background effects that provide quick visual adaptation without involving third-party designers is justified.

To avoid ethical risks, clients should be allowed to agree on the extent to which AI processing is applied and to create transparent image editing rules that preserve the event's authenticity. In a professional environment, it is also advisable to

introduce internal standards for the use of artificial intelligence technologies that regulate the limits of automation while preserving the creative autonomy of the author.

Another relevant area is the development of multi-tool platforms that combine photo and video processing in a single environment with artificial intelligence modules; this ensures consistency of style and increases the speed of order fulfillment, which is a key factor in competitiveness in the modern wedding market.

Conclusions. The study found that integrating artificial intelligence and deep learning technologies into creating wedding photo and video content contributes to automation, personalization, and improvement of the artistic quality of the material. It has been determined that the adaptation of artificial intelligence models to the content's stylistic, compositional and emotional requirements is possible through specialized training and scenario-based processing logic. The paper identifies the key problems of implementing artificial intelligence and deep learning technologies: technical limitations, risks of style standardization, loss of creative control, and ethical threats to the authenticity of images. The author recommends using artificial intelligence tools to complement the author's approach, developing personalized models, implementing internal editing standards, and mastering multi-tool platforms.

Prospects for further research include the development of specialized datasets, hybrid quality assessment models, and adaptive interfaces for the creativity of photographers and videographers when creating wedding content.

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